

INFRA-RED STUDIES OF STERCULIC ACID AND SOME RELATED COMPOUNDS

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Methyl esters of four carboxylic acids related to sterculic acid were synthetically prepared. Their infra-red absorption spectra along with those of sterculic and dihydrosterculic acids were examined. All afforded absorption bands in the 9.9μ region, characteristic of the cyclopropane ring. The presence of bands due to unsaturation in sterculic acid and their absence in the two synthetic cyclopropene acids indicate that the constitution of sterculic acid as ω -(2-*n*-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic acid is most probably not correct. The iodine and diene values of sterculic acid and the above compounds also lead to similar conclusions.

Sterculic acid, the major component of the kernel oil of *Sterculia foetida*, was recently isolated by Nunn (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 313) and was assigned the constitution ω -(2-*n*-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic acid (I). This being an unusual fatty acid on account of its marked tendency towards polymerisation, further work on its constitution was undertaken.

It is difficult to establish the presence of a cyclopropane ring in an organic molecule by ultraviolet absorption spectra or chemical means. Infra-red absorption studies have been solely employed until now for the identification of such a ring. cycloPropane itself has been found to absorb at 11.55μ and 9.75μ by Bartleson, Burk and Lankelma (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2513). Derfer, Pickett and Boord (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 2432) from their study of fourteen cyclopropane derivatives found that all of them showed strong absorption in the 9.80 - 10μ region, the band centred at about 9.90μ , ascribed by Herzberg as the symmetric vibration of the cyclopropyl ring ("Infra-red and Raman Spectra of Polyatomic Molecules," p. 352, New York, D. Van Nostrand Co., 1945), being a dependable tool for identifying the cyclopropane ring. Their results have been confirmed by Marrison (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1614), Smith and Rogier (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3840) and Wiberley and Bunce (*Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 623). Nunn (*loc. cit.*) has based his structure (I) for sterculic acid mainly on the strong band at 9.8μ in the infra-red spectrum of dihydrosterculic acid, analogous to that in the C_{12} -acid isolated from *Lactobacillus arabinosus* by Hoffmann and Lucas (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4328). He did not, however, take the infra-red of the sterculic acid itself. In this communication the infra-red studies of sterculic acid and dihydrosterculic acid have been recorded in addition to those of the methyl esters of synthetic Δ -2-*n*-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic acid (I), ω -(2-*n*-octylcyclopropyl)-octanoic acid (II), ω -(2-*n*-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-dodecanoic acid (III) and ω -(2-*n*-octylcyclopropyl)-dodecanoic acid (IV). These results show that the structure (I) for sterculic acid is not well founded.

(V)

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Sterculic Acid.—Nunn (*loc. cit.*) isolated sterculic acid through urea complexes fractionation, but this was not followed as it involved some heating operation to which the acid was found to be especially susceptible. In this laboratory the acid was obtained by low-temperature fractional crystallisation technique from the total fatty acids of the oil (Varma, Nath and Aggarwal, *Oils & Oil-seeds J.*, 1954, 7, No 6, 10), m.p. 19° ; n_D^{25} , 1.4758; I.V. (Wijs), 98.2; Diene value, 40.3. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 11.4. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.5; H, 11.56 per cent).

Dihydrosterculic Acid.—Sterculic acid (92.4 mg.) in ethanol in the presence of palladised calcium carbonate (2%) absorbed 7.2 c.c. of hydrogen (nearly one mole). The solid product after crystallisation from acetone melted at $39-40^\circ$; I.V. (Wijs), 76.5. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 12.2. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.0; H, 12.16 per cent).

ω -(2-n-Octylcyclopropyl)-octanoic Methyl Ester (II).—A solution of pure oleic acid (5 g) in anhydrous ethyl ether was treated with excess of diazomethane. The product after removal of the solvent under reduced pressure was dissolved in light petroleum (b.p. $40^\circ-60^\circ$) and chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl ether as eluant, yielding the main fraction (2.1 g.), m.p. -1° ; n_D^{25} , 1.4443; I.V., 76.5; Diene value, 3.2. (Found: C, 77.9; H, 12.1. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.4; H, 12.3 per cent).

ω -(2-n-Octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic Methyl Ester (I).—Stearolic acid (10 g.), prepared by the method of Adkins and Burks ('Org. Syntheses', 27, p. 76; m.p. 48°), was dissolved in anhydrous ethyl ether, allowed to react with excess of diazomethane and worked up as above, furnishing a product (4.3 g.), m.p. 16° ; n_D^{25} , 1.4489; I.V., 80.6; Diene value, 5.3. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 11.8. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.9; H, 11.8 per cent).

The compound (I) was further purified by distilling at $105^\circ-110^\circ/4$ mm. without any sign of decomposition and the distillate exhibited almost the same characteristics as above.

ω -(2-n-Octylcyclopropyl)-dodecanoic Methyl Ester (IV).—Purified erucic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous ethyl ether and treated with excess of diazomethane. The resulting product, after chromatographic separation over silica gel in light petroleum (40°-60°) furnished a main fraction (4.9 g.) melting at -15°; n_D^{20} , 1.4514; I.V., 60.8; Diene value, 1.7. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 12.4. $C_{24}H_{46}O_2$ requires C, 78.7; H, 12.65 per cent).

ω -(2-n-Octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-dodecanoic Methyl Ester (III).—A solution of behenic acid (10 g., m.p. 58°) (prepared from erucic acid by a method parallel to that of stearolic acid) in anhydrous ethyl ether was treated with excess of diazomethane, and the product after removal of the solvent was dissolved in light petroleum and chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl ether as eluant, yielding a product (4.1 g.), m.p. 18°; n_D^{20} , 1.4520; I.V., 68.8; Diene value, 5.0. (Found: C, 78.6; H, 11.9. $C_{24}H_{44}O_2$ requires C, 79.1; H, 12.2 per cent).

Infra-red Spectra.—The data recorded were obtained with a Grubb-Parsons spectrometer having a sodium chloride prism. All the above substances were examined in a solution of known concentration in purified carbon tetrachloride in the region 2.8 μ to 7 μ and carbon disulphide in the region 7 μ to 15 μ in a rock salt cell having a capacity of 0.1 ml.

FIG. 1

Curve 1 refers to sterculic acid and curve 2 to ω -(2-n-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic methyl ester.

DISCUSSION

The infra-red absorption spectra of sterculic acid and ω -(2-n-cycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic methyl ester (I) are shown in Fig. 1 as wave-lengths vs. percentage absorption. Dihydrosterculic acid and the synthetic methyl esters prepared from oleic (II), erucic (IV) and behenic (III) acids furnished absorption spectra similar to that of ω -(2-n-octylcycloprop-1-enyl)-octanoic acid.

The absorption bands of both the acids and the synthetic acid esters with the exception of the $9.8\text{-}10\mu$ are very similar to those of long-chain fatty acids and their esters.

Sterculic acid, dihydrosterculic acid and the four synthetic acid esters (I-IV) all show bands in the $9.8\text{-}10\mu$ region, sterculic acid itself absorbing strongly at 9.92μ associated with a weaker band at 9.70μ , and the dihydrosterculic acid and the acid esters showing bands of medium intensity at 9.90μ . Since all the four synthetic methyl esters of the acids (I-IV) have exhibited identical bands in this region, there may be a possibility that the characteristic bands for *cyclopropane* and *cyclopropene* derivatives occupy the same position.

The spectrum of sterculic acid also exhibits bands of nearly medium intensity at 6.09μ and 14.50μ due to unsaturation. These bands vanish on the catalytic hydrogenation of the acid to dihydrosterculic acid and are also absent in the spectra of two synthetic *cyclopropene* acid esters (I and III). The presence of a double bond inside the three-membered carbon ring in sterculic acid, as shown by Nunn (*loc. cit.*), therefore appears doubtful.

Further points against the proposed structure ascribed by Nunn to sterculic acid are brought out by the facts that the iodine values of both synthetically prepared ω -(2-*n*-octyl*cycloprop-1-enyl*)-octanoic and -dodecanoic methyl esters (I and III) are somewhat less than one double bond (80.6 and 68.8 as against 81.8 and 69.7 respectively) and they have almost negligible diene values (5.3 and 5.0 respectively.) The iodine value of sterculic acid, however, is more than one double bond (98.2) and it also possesses sufficiently high diene value (40.3). The typical unsaturation of *cyclopropane* ring compounds towards some specific additive reagents has been demonstrated by Kohler and Conant (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1404). This fact has also been observed in the present study of the iodine values of dihydrosterculic acid and the two synthetic *cyclopropane* compounds (II and IV). The results mentioned above therefore show that the double bond in sterculic acid probably is outside the three-membered carbon ring and not as shown by Nunn (I).

A structure (V) for sterculic acid has already been proposed by Verma, Nath and Aggarwal (*Nature*, 1955, **175**, 84) and further work for its confirmation is in progress.